

LINKING TEACHERS' EDUCATIONAL INNOVATION, SATISFACTION AND JOB PERFORMANCE IN MUHAMMADIYAH HIGH SCHOOLS IN EAST JAVA WITH COMPETENCE, WORK LIFE QUALITY, AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

Muhammadiyah, as a large organization with 558 high schools throughout Indonesia and 85 of them are in East Java, has a significant contribution to education, showing the important role of Muhammadiyah high schools in the world of education. Quality education is heavily reliant on the performance of teachers, and the Merdeka Mengajar Platform aims to encourage the development of innovative teaching methods. This study seeks to demonstrate and assess the impact of competency, quality of work life, and information technology on educational innovation, job satisfaction, and the performance of teachers. This quantitative research collected primary data with questionnaire from 347 Muhammadiyah High Schools teachers in East Java and analyzed using AMOS 20. The findings indicate that competency has a positive and significant influence on teacher innovation and performance, but its impact on teacher job satisfaction insignificantly. Quality of work life has a positive and significant effect on teacher innovation and job satisfaction, but its impact on teacher performance insignificantly. Information technology has a positive and significant effect on teacher innovation, as well as a positive and significant impact on teacher job satisfaction and performance. Innovation has a positive and insignificant effect on teacher job satisfaction, but a positive and significant impact on teacher performance. Finally, job satisfaction has a positive and insignificant impact on teacher performance.

Keywords: Competence, Quality of Work Life, Information Technology, Educational Innovation, Job Performance.

INTRODUCTION

It is noteworthy that education statistics data for 2022/2023 indicate a significant presence of private senior high schools in Indonesia, with 53.52% being private schools and 46.48% public schools. This distribution underscores the substantial role played by private high schools, particularly in East Java where there are 1,641 high schools, of which 1,208 are private schools, reflecting a high concentration of schools in the province. Additionally, the influence of Muhammadiyah in the education sector is palpable, with 558 high schools established throughout the country and 85 in East Java, demonstrating its widespread impact.

The pivotal role of teacher competence in enhancing performance is well-documented in the literature. Sulistyowati (2018) defines competence as encompassing the skills, knowledge, and work attitudes necessary to meet job standards, and Rohman (2020) highlights the importance of competence in improving teacher professionalism, including pedagogical, social, and professional skills that influence performance.

Moreover, studies by Sulistyowati (2018) and Lengkey (2021) reaffirm the positive effect of competence, innovation, and creativity on employee performance, underscoring their importance in the work environment. Notably, the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology (Kemendikbudristek) launched the Merdeka Mengajar (PMM) Platform in 2022 to facilitate teachers' access to training and learning resources, thereby aiming to enhance education and teaching quality across Indonesia.

Given the aforementioned context, an exploration of the influence of competency, quality of work life, and information technology on educational innovation, job satisfaction, and teacher performance at SMA Muhammadiyah East Java appears to be a pertinent area of study. This investigation aligns with the current discourse on teacher competence and innovation in improving educational outcomes and teacher performance in various sectors.

Quality of Work Life

In the 1980s, the concept of Quality of Work Life (QWL) included various aspects such as organization, work environment, and partnership. It was similar to the idea of "humanization of work" in Germany and "improvement of working conditions" in France. QWL focuses not only on psychological aspects, but also on social aspects, which encompass employee participation and responsibility. According to Nawawi (2008), companies need to create a sense of security and job satisfaction in order to achieve their goals. Cascio (2006) added that QWL can be understood as employee perceptions of security, job satisfaction, and self-development opportunities, or as organizational goals through specific policies.

Bernardin & Russel (2013) define QWL as the level of employee satisfaction, motivation, involvement, and commitment to their work. Luthans (2006) stated that QWL is a combination of human and company effectiveness, emphasizing participation in problem-solving and decision-making. The main components of QWL include the work environment, organizational culture and climate, work relationships, training and development, compensation, facilities, and balance between work and personal life. QWL is assessed through dimensions such as employee health and well-being, job security, job satisfaction, competency development, and work-life balance, all of which are important for creating a healthy and productive work environment.

Educational Innovation

The evolving landscape of education necessitates teachers to adapt to changing learning behaviors, particularly among millennial learners in urban communities with middle to upper socioeconomic levels. These students are adept at multitasking and accessing information from diverse sources simultaneously. Consequently, educators must develop innovative strategies to

captivate students' interest and effectively guide their learning process. Purdy (1968) describes educational innovation as the utilization of resources in novel ways to enhance performance, while Agabi (2002) views it as a deliberate transformation across various facets of education to bolster performance.

It's essential to note that innovation in education encompasses not only information technology but also new ideas and learning paradigms. For instance, the incorporation of blogs by educators and assigning tasks that involve procuring test questions from blogs exemplify innovative approaches. Information technology fosters heightened collaboration among students, reshaping their learning methods, albeit necessitating appropriate supervision by teachers. Rogers (2003) stresses that for innovation to be embraced by society, it should offer a relative advantage, be compatible, exhibit manageable complexity, provide an opportunity for testing, and offer clear observability.

In various countries, Briggs (2011) observes an upsurge in innovative learning practices, with educators increasingly linking learning to real-world applications and nurturing students' critical thinking abilities. Furthermore, the assessment of student learning outcomes has transitioned from conventional methods to strategies such as collective assessment that integrates online and offline sources of information. Educational institutions have also innovated by introducing new training initiatives, interest groups, and partnerships with stakeholders to evaluate educational and institutional outcomes.

Teacher Performance

Employee performance encompasses measurable actions, behaviors, and outcomes tied to organizational objectives and their contributions. According to Jimoh (2008), evaluating employee performance necessitates observers to assess individual behavioral propensities. Performance assessment can encompass aspects such as quantity, quality, efficiency, professionalism, and creativity, as delineated by Mangkunegara (2015). Bernardin & Russel (2013) further stated that performance emanates from work aligned with organizational goals and efficiency. In the realm of education, teacher performance plays a pivotal role in student success, necessitating the ability to design, execute, and appraise learning. Teachers should exhibit professional competence and scholastic abilities that bolster the teaching and learning process. The Republic of Indonesia Law Number 14 of 2005 governs the professional responsibilities of teachers, encompassing the planning of high-quality learning experiences and the evaluation of learning outcomes. Various factors, such as principal leadership, school climate, and prevailing expectations, can influence teacher performance.

To enhance the proficiency of educational personnel and students' learning accomplishments, principals can engage teachers in training and offer opportunities for ongoing learning. Mulyasa (2021) underscored the significance of utilizing learning time effectively and promoting transparent evaluation of learning outcomes. Performance dimensions, outlined by Fautisno Cardoso Gomes (2013), encompass factors such as the quantity and quality of work, job knowledge, creativity, cooperation, self-awareness, initiative, and personal attributes, all of which are utilized to assess employee performance.

Research Hypothesis

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

Based on the conceptual framework described above, the hypotheses proposed in the research are:

- H1 : Competence has a significant influence on the Teaching Innovation*
- H2 : Competence has a significant influence on the Work Satisfaction*
- H3 : Competence has a significant influence on the Teaching Performance*
- H4 : Quality of Work-Life has a significant influence on the Teaching Innovation*
- H5 : Quality of Work-Life has a significant influence on the Work Satisfaction*
- H6 : Quality of Work-Life has a significant influence on the Teaching Performance*
- H7 : Information Technology has a significant influence on the Teaching Innovation*
- H8 : Information Technology has a significant influence on the Work Satisfaction*
- H9 : Information Technology has a significant influence on the Teaching Performance*
- H10 : Teaching Innovation has a significant influence on the Work Satisfaction*
- H11 : Teaching Innovation has a significant influence on the Teacher Performance*
- H12 : Work Satisfaction has a significant influence on the Teacher Performance*

METHODS

This research is an explanatory causal study that aims to explain the relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables. As a replication study, the hypothesis test results must be consistent with previous studies conducted under different conditions. The research involves

collecting data from specific locations through methods such as questionnaires, tests, and interviews.

Participants

The study was carried out on high school teachers affiliated with Muhammadiyah across East Java in January 2022, with a total population of 2,635 teachers. A sample of 347 teachers was selected using the Slovin technique and the Proportional Random Sampling method from 38 cities and districts in East Java.

Procedure

Primary data, gathered through a questionnaire using a five-point Likert scale, was collected from mid-January 2021 to the end of February 2023. Additionally, secondary data from sources such as books, literature, articles, journals, and the Internet was also utilized to support the theoretical framework. The study employed SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) with AMOS 22 software for data processing and analysis.

RESULTS

Demographics

The demographic data of the respondents indicates that the teaching profession in Muhammadiyah High Schools in East Java is predominantly female, with 59.3% compared to 40.7% male teachers. This trend reflects a global pattern where the education sector, especially at the secondary school level, is often occupied by more women, possibly due to gender stereotypes associating women with caregiving and education roles.

Table 1: Respondent's demographics.

Profiles	Sub-profiles	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	146	40,7
	Female	213	59,3
Age	21-30y.o	118	32,9
	31-40y.o	100	27,9
	41-50y.o	91	25,3
	Older than 50y.o	50	13,9
Education level	Hrigh school	23	6,4
	Undergraduate	325	90,5
	Post graduate	11	3,1
Working Tenure	1-5 years	138	38,4
	>5-10 years	55	15,3
	>10-15 years	46	12,8
	>15-20 years	45	12,5
	Over 20 years	75	20,9

In terms of age, the majority of teachers fall within the 21-30 years range (32.9%), with significant numbers in the age groups of 31-40 years (27.9%) and 41-50 years (25.3%). Teachers over 50 years old make up only 13.9%, indicating good generational turnover in this profession. Moreover, the data reveals that the majority of teachers hold a bachelor's degree

(90.5%), demonstrating a strong commitment to professionalism. Although 6.4% of teachers have a high school education, the presence of 3.1% with postgraduate education suggests a robust academic foundation to enhance the effectiveness of teaching practices.

Concerning work experience, most teachers have 1-5 years of experience (38.4%), indicating the presence of new teachers with innovative potential, while 20.9% have more than 20 years of experience, signifying the presence of highly experienced teachers. This combination fosters a positive dynamic in the educational environment, where experienced teachers can share knowledge with newer teachers, while the latter bring fresh energy and innovative approaches. In summary, the distribution of age, education, and work experience demonstrates that the teaching profession in Muhammadiyah high schools in East Java comprises relatively young, highly educated individuals with diverse experiences, thereby making a positive contribution to the education process.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing of the direct influence of each research variable can be explained as follows:

Table 2: Respondent's demographics.

Hip.	Pengaruh Langsung	Std. Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P value	Keputusan Hipotesis
H ₁	X1 → Z1	0,378*	0,083	7,462	0,000	ACCEPTED
H ₂	X1 → Z2	0,112 <i>n.s</i>	0,061	1,843	0,065	REJECTED
H ₃	X1 → Y	0,249*	0,073	4,102	0,000	ACCEPTED
H ₄	X2 → Z1	0,252*	0,059	4,620	0,000	ACCEPTED
H ₅	X2 → Z2	0,440*	0,049	6,051	0,000	ACCEPTED
H ₆	X2 → Y	0,095 <i>n.s</i>	0,053	1,424	0,154	REJECTED
H ₇	X3 → Z1	0,401*	0,057	6,927	0,000	ACCEPTED
H ₈	X3 → Z2	0,296*	0,044	4,108	0,000	ACCEPTED
H ₉	X3 → Y	0,173*	0,050	2,465	0,014	ACCEPTED
H ₁₀	Z1 → Z2	0,026 <i>n.s</i>	0,051	0,311	0,755	REJECTED
H ₁₁	Z1 → Y	0,380*	0,064	4,356	0,000	ACCEPTED
H ₁₂	Z2 → Y	0,029 <i>n.s</i>	0,084	0,406	0,685	REJECTED

- 1) The coefficient of influence of competence on educational innovation is significant, with a CR value of 7.462 and a p-value of 0.000. This positive influence (coefficient of 0.378) indicates that higher teacher competence leads to greater educational innovation, supporting the acceptance of the first hypothesis (H1). Descriptive analysis reveals that the level of innovation among teachers at Muhammadiyah Senior High Schools in East Java is rated as good. The highest indicator of innovation is observed in the enhancement of innovative learning practices, with a mean score of 4.28. On the other hand, educational organizational innovation shows the lowest indicator with a mean score of 3.81. These findings suggest that teacher competence plays a crucial role in fostering innovation. Higher competence enables teachers to gain a deeper understanding of education and equips them with the necessary skills to identify student requirements and adapt their teaching methods in creative and innovative ways.

- 2) The coefficient of influence of competence on job satisfaction is insignificant, with a CR value of 1.843 and a p-value of 0.065. The low coefficient of 0.112 suggests that increased teacher competence does not significantly impact job satisfaction, leading to the rejection of the second hypothesis (H2). The descriptive analysis indicates that Muhammadiyah high school teachers in East Java exhibit a high level of competence, particularly in their personality competence (mean 4.37) and pedagogical competence (mean 4.2). The teachers' job satisfaction is perceived to be moderate, with the highest indicator being work attendance (mean 4.29) and the lowest being a sense of fairness in receiving rewards (mean 3.23) and demonstrations or other destructive behavior (mean 2.40). These findings suggest that competence alone does not always determine teacher job satisfaction, as other factors, such as the work environment, also play a significant role.
- 3) The coefficient of influence of competence on teacher performance is significant, with a CR value of 4.102 and a p-value of 0.000. A positive coefficient of 0.249 shows that higher competence improves teacher performance, validating the third hypothesis (H3). The descriptive analysis reveals that teachers at Muhammadiyah Senior High Schools in East Java displayed high ratings for their competencies, particularly in personality and professionalism, scoring 4.37 and 4.35 respectively. Although the pedagogical competency scored slightly lower at 4.20, it still reflects a high level, suggesting potential areas for further development. The teachers' performance was also assessed as very commendable. It was observed that teachers with elevated competencies tend to exhibit greater effectiveness in teaching, classroom management, and adapting teaching methods to students' needs, leading to an overall enhancement in their performance.
- 4) The coefficient of influence of quality of work life on educational innovation is significant, with a CR value of 4.620 and a p-value of 0.000. A coefficient of 0.252 indicates that better work quality boosts educational innovation, supporting the fourth hypothesis (H4). A positive work environment, support from colleagues and management, and a healthy work-life balance can enhance teacher satisfaction. This, in turn, makes them more receptive to new ideas and innovations in the learning process. When teachers feel valued and supported, they are more inclined to engage in developing innovations, fostering an environment conducive to positive change.
- 5) The coefficient of influence of quality of work life on job satisfaction is significant, with a CR value of 6.051 and a p-value of 0.000. With a coefficient of 0.440, this shows that improved work quality increases job satisfaction, validating the fifth hypothesis (H5). Teachers' job satisfaction is influenced by various factors, including the quality of the work environment, work-life balance, and recognition for their contributions. Happy and satisfied teachers tend to have higher levels of job satisfaction when they feel supported and appreciated in their work environment. This support and recognition motivate them to give their best to the school.
- 6) The coefficient of influence of quality of work life on teacher performance is insignificant, with a CR value of 1.424 and a p-value of 0.154. The low coefficient of 0.095 means that quality of work life does not significantly impact teacher performance, leading to the

rejection of the sixth hypothesis (H6). Teacher job satisfaction is affected by several factors, including the quality of the work environment, work-life balance, and recognition for their contributions. Happy and content teachers are often the result of a supportive and appreciative work environment, which in turn leads to higher job satisfaction and increased motivation to perform well at school.

- 7) The coefficient of influence of information technology on educational innovation is significant, with a CR value of 6.927 and a p-value of 0.000. The positive coefficient of 0.401 indicates that higher use of information technology enhances educational innovation, supporting the seventh hypothesis (H7). "Information technology allows for easier access to educational resources, including interactive learning materials, learning software, and online learning platforms. Teachers can use a variety of tools and applications to design more engaging and effective learning experiences. Additionally, information technology enables the implementation of innovative teaching methods, such as project-based learning and game-based learning."
- 8) The coefficient of influence of information technology on job satisfaction is significant, with a CR value of 4.108 and a p-value of 0.000. A coefficient of 0.296 shows that increased use of information technology improves job satisfaction, validating the eighth hypothesis (H8). The use of information technology can improve the efficiency of administrative tasks, such as student assessment, reporting, and classroom management. With information technology, teachers can access educational resources more easily and quickly, which can reduce their workload. Integrating information technology into the learning process can lead to increased teacher job satisfaction, as it allows for the creation of more engaging and meaningful learning experiences for students.
- 9) The coefficient of influence of information technology on teacher performance is significant, with a CR value of 2.465 and a p-value of 0.014. The coefficient of 0.173 indicates that better use of information technology enhances teacher performance, supporting the ninth hypothesis (H9). The use of information technology can enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of the learning process. With improved access to online learning resources, teachers are able to deliver materials in a more engaging and interactive manner. Furthermore, information technology enables teachers to personalize students' learning experiences, identify their weaknesses, and provide feedback more promptly. As a result, proficient use of information technology by teachers tends to lead to better performance, as it allows them to offer a more enhanced learning experience to their students.
- 10) The coefficient of influence of educational innovation on job satisfaction is insignificant, with a CR value of 0.311 and a p-value of 0.755. The coefficient of 0.026 suggests that educational innovation does not significantly affect job satisfaction, leading to the rejection of the tenth hypothesis (H10). "While educational innovation can enhance learning effectiveness, job satisfaction does not always align with the level of innovation. A teacher may feel content with their job due to a good working environment or a satisfactory salary, even if the level of innovation in learning remains low."

- 11) The coefficient of influence of educational innovation on teacher performance is significant, with a CR value of 4.356 and a p-value of 0.000. The coefficient of 0.380 indicates that higher educational innovation improves teacher performance, validating the eleventh hypothesis (H11). "Educational innovation has the potential to enhance the learning process and improve student learning outcomes. Teachers who embrace educational innovation are often more creative in designing learning experiences, better able to meet student needs, and have a positive impact on student learning outcomes. Teacher performance can be evaluated based on their ability to meet learning objectives and enhance student competencies."
- 12) The coefficient of influence of job satisfaction on teacher performance is insignificant, with a CR value of 0.406 and a p-value of 0.685. The low coefficient of 0.029 means that increased job satisfaction does not significantly impact teacher performance, leading to the rejection of the twelfth hypothesis (H12). Job satisfaction is linked to teacher well-being, but it may not always directly correlate with performance. Other factors like competence can have a greater impact on teacher performance. A teacher may be content with their job, but without the necessary skills, their performance may still be lacking."

DISCUSSION

Competence can directly influence teacher performance or indirectly do so through educational innovation. Overall, competence is the most significant factor in improving teacher performance. While teacher competence is generally high, there are areas that need further attention. Indicators of pedagogical competence and social competence are considered the lowest compared to other indicators, showing the need to enhance teachers' skills in designing effective learning and their ability to interact and communicate with students, colleagues, and parents. Muhammadiyah High Schools in East Java could consider developing special training programs focusing on these areas, including innovative teaching techniques, classroom management strategies, and effective communication skills.

The quality of work life has an indirect influence on teacher performance through educational innovation. Although its direct influence is not significant, it still significantly contributes to improving teacher performance overall. The lowest-rated quality of work-life indicators are job security, salary, and benefits. Therefore, SMA Muhammadiyah should consider strategic steps to improve working conditions, focusing on job security and fair compensation for each teacher. This may include improving workplace security, protection against violence, and fair salaries and benefits based on education and experience. Furthermore, fair career development opportunities should be provided to each teacher.

Information technology can directly influence teacher performance or indirectly through educational innovation as a mediator. Competence is also a key factor contributing to improving teacher performance. Factors such as informational sophistication and managerial sophistication play important roles in influencing teacher performance through the use of information technology. To improve teacher performance, SMA Muhammadiyah in East Java can take strategic steps such as developing technological infrastructure. This involves investing

in fast internet access, sophisticated hardware, and learning support software to allow teachers to optimally utilize information technology in the learning process. Integrating information technology into the learning curriculum is also necessary to create a more interactive and engaging learning experience for students. Educational innovation can also directly influence teacher performance significantly. The focus should be on improving innovative learning practices. Muhammadiyah High Schools in East Java should design the curriculum to encourage innovative learning practices that are responsive to students' needs and interests. This can be achieved through technology integration, collaborative projects, and student-centered teaching methods. Additionally, teachers need support in implementing active and problem-based learning approaches.

Teacher job satisfaction is of less priority as it has a small impact on their performance. Thus, increasing teacher satisfaction is not an urgent issue to be addressed at the moment as the indicators relating to job satisfaction are currently considered high. "approaches that encourage students to be actively involved in the learning process, which will improve innovative learning practices. Teacher job satisfaction is the last priority because it has a small (insignificant) impact on their performance. Increasing teacher satisfaction is still not urgent to be improved, because the indicators that provide the greatest contribution to increasing job satisfaction based on factor loading are feelings of happiness with the current position and willingness to accept work with full responsibility. Both of these indicators are currently still considered high. Furthermore, regarding the indicator of satisfaction with rewards, it is indeed not high, but this indicator also does not have a large weight in reflecting teacher job satisfaction.

Significance of the Study:

The research findings suggest theoretical implications by establishing a conceptual framework model that incorporates the elements of employee well-being, Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), and individual performance in mediating the relationship between happiness at work and exhaustion, based on goal setting theory. The results also reveal a model for enhancing individual performance through employee well-being, OCB, and another model for improving individual performance through happiness at work and reducing exhaustion.

In addition to this, the research indicates a model for increasing individual performance through employee well-being and OCB based on social exchange theory, as well as a model for enhancing work happiness and decreasing exhaustion.

Practical implications

The findings of this study suggest that, in order to enhance the performance of teachers in Muhammadiyah Senior High Schools in East Java, the primary focus should be on improving teacher competency and educational innovation, as these factors have the greatest impact on performance. Although information technology and quality of work life are also important, their influence is lower and often indirect through educational innovation as a mediator. In contrast, teacher job satisfaction was found to have an insignificant influence on performance, making it the least priority. These findings offer valuable guidance for effectively managing human resources in educational institutions by highlighting the scale of priorities.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the study indicated that out of the twelve hypotheses proposed, only eight were supported, consistent with the established theory and prior research. Specifically, hypotheses 1, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, and 11 were found to be supported. However, the remaining four hypotheses, 2, 6, 10, and 12, were not supported. These hypotheses suggested that higher teacher competence does not significantly impact job satisfaction, better quality of work life does not effectively improve teacher performance, increased educational innovation does not substantially impact teacher job satisfaction, and higher teacher job satisfaction does not significantly enhance performance.

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